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Teachers' motivational strategies: Mediating effect of parental involvement for positive student outcomes

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the effectiveness of Teachers' Motivational Strategies in promoting parental involvement and the possible impacts on schooling outcomes of elementary pupils in Magaud, Loreto, Agusan del Sur. The research employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design, utilizing a survey questionnaire as the primary data-gathering tool. The participants were the parents whose children are officially enrolled in Magaud Elementary School from Kindergarten up to Grade Six. A modified survey questionnaire was developed that focuses on the teacher's motivational strategies and parental involvement. The grades were gathered as secondary data that serve as students' outcomes. The data collected were analyzed using statistical methods such as mean, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and Analysis of Variance (ANOVA). The results showed a high level of teachers' motivational strategies and parental involvement. The findings revealed that parents tend to maintain a relatively consistent level of involvement in their children's education, regardless of whether their child is in the early or later years of elementary schooling. There was a negligible positive relationship between parental involvement and student outcomes.

Keywords: Teacher's Motivational Strategies; Parental Involvement; Student Outcome; Descriptive-Correlational Study

1. Introduction

The role of parents in the success of students has been well noted as one of the strongest factors. As many researchers have discovered, parental participation in the education of a child has always been reported to be positively linked to the academic achievement of a child [1-4]. The useful impact of parental involvement in the education of a child is great, however, one of the most obvious ones is help with school tasks [5]. However, parental involvement can be particularly challenging for students when their parents are preoccupied with work, especially in families with limited financial resources. Teachers' motivational strategies can play a crucial role in addressing this issue. These strategies can develop a deeper understanding of the long-term benefits of parental involvement.

Many studies in many parts of the world have proved that parental involvement in their offspring is important. This is the case shown by Jeynes [6] in a study conducted in California, United States, which indicated a positive relation between active parental involvement and academic achievement, social growth, and general well-being of the student. When parents are involved in the educational process of their children either by engaging in homework assistance arrangements, or organizing school related events like visiting the school, there is the likelihood that such students will achieve good grades, learn how to socialize, and possess good behavioral results [7]. In the Philippines settings, particularly in different schools of Manolo Fortich IV District, Division of Bukidnon, the study of Escol and Alcopra [8] parental involvement demonstrated a significant relationship with learners' academic performance.

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Studies also indicate that strong involvement in academic lives of children by parents will lead students to better academic outcomes, better social behaviors and strong emotional wellbeing [9]. Research indicates that, parents who take part in children's studies activities like helping in their homework, participating in school activities and keeping in touch with teachers are beneficial to academic achievement of children [10].

In rural areas like Magaud, Loreto in Agusan del Sur, there is a lack of research on effective strategies to motivate parental involvement in education. While studies show a positive link between parental engagement and student outcomes, most focus on urban settings and overlook the challenges faced by rural families. Based on the researcher's experience as a rural public-school educator, many parents prioritize livelihood activities such as farming or selling produce, leaving limited time for school participation. Moreover, while Brigada Eskwela promotes community participation, there is limited empirical evidence on how teachers' motivational strategies can directly influence the level of parental involvement in students' day-to-day educational activities.

To date, there are currently limited studies and written works available about the enhancement of student outcomes using motivational strategies of teachers to the parents involved in education in Magaud, Loreto, Agusan del Sur. Therefore, the researcher wanted to conduct this study to explore the mediating effect of teacher motivational strategies on the parents in improving the students' performance.

2. Materials and Methods

This study employed a quantitative descriptive-correlational research design, which assessed the effectiveness of teachers' motivational strategies in promoting parental involvement and the possible impacts on students' outcomes. Data were collected from Magaud Elementary School. The respondents were the 384 parents whose children were attending in the 2024-2025 school year. In case parents who had multiple children attending school at different grade levels received multiple survey questionnaires specific to their child.

The study utilized a modified questionnaire from the study of Epstein et al. [7], which included the teacher's motivational strategies and Jekonia [11] for parental involvement. The grades of the students were also collected to identify the students' outcomes. The questionnaire underwent validation by experts, followed by a pilot test to refine the instrument before distribution.

Data were analyzed using basic descriptive statistics, such as mean, to interpret the levels regarding teachers' motivational strategies and parental involvement. Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient to identify the significant relationship between parental involvement and student outcomes. Lastly, ANOVA was utilized to determine the significant difference in parental involvement when grouped according to grade level.

3. Results and Discussion

The effectiveness of the motivational strategies of teachers has been reported in Table 1. According to the results, parenting received the highest mean of 4.19 and the descriptive equivalent was high with a descriptive of 3 on a scale of 1 being low and 5 being high which meant that teachers usually assist all families to comprehend child and adolescent development and create a home environment to foster children as students. Conversely, volunteering received the lowest mean of 4.02 although it does have the same descriptive expression of high and this means that teachers tend to recruit and organize parents to assist the teachers as well as the learners. In addition to this, the effectiveness of the motivational strategies used by teachers bore a weighted mean of 4.12 whose descriptive equivalent was high.

The results indicate that teachers exhibit a high level of motivational strategies in terms of parenting. Many teachers are mindful of the cultural backgrounds of their students, showing respect and understanding toward the diversity in their classrooms. This kind of attitude not only strengthens the relationship between home and school but also helps students feel more accepted and supported. On the other hand, while teachers are doing well overall, there seems to be less focus on activities like home visits or neighborhood meetings.

The results align with existing literature emphasizing the importance of culturally responsive practices and active parental involvement in promoting student success. Gay [12] highlights that culturally responsive teaching fosters mutual respect and enhances communication between schools and diverse families. Similarly, Epstein [13] asserts that when educators recognize and support the role of families, particularly by honoring their cultural contexts, students benefit academically and socially. However, Sheldon and Epstein [14] note that while strategies like home visits can deepen trust and communication, they are often constrained by logistical barriers.

These results support what researchers have long recognized about the importance of effective school-to-home communication. Epstein [13] pointed out that when teachers consistently share clear and timely information with families, it strengthens collaboration and improves student outcomes. At the same time, researchers like Goodall and Montgomery [15] revealed that not all families have equal access to digital resources, and that inclusive communication strategies, such as providing printed materials or in-person updates, can make a big difference. Supporting this, Henderson and Mapp [16] highlighted that when schools adapt their communication methods to meet families' diverse needs, engagement becomes more meaningful and sustainable.

Table 1 Level of Effectiveness of Teachers' Motivational Strategies

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Parenting	4.19	High
Communicating	4.09	High
Volunteering	4.02	High
Learning at Home	4.18	High
Decision making	4.13	High
Collaborating with the community	4.10	High
Overall	4.12	High

Table 2 presents the parental involvement in Elementary School. Based on the results, home-based involvement activities garnered the highest mean of 4.11, with a descriptive equivalent of 'high', indicating that parents often support their child's learning in their study at home. On the other hand, school-based involvement activities garnered the lowest mean of 4.00, but still have a descriptive equivalent of high, indicating that teachers often participate in school-related activities. Moreover, the parental involvement had a weighted mean of 4.05 with a descriptive equivalent of high.

The results show that parents are highly engaged in supporting their children's education from home, particularly when it comes to attending to their basic needs. Many parents are making consistent efforts to ensure their children are well-fed, dressed appropriately, and ready to participate in school activities. This reflects a deep sense of care and responsibility, which is foundational for student success. However, maintaining household rules and discipline at home appears to be a slightly more challenging area for some parents. This could stem from a variety of factors, such as time constraints, parenting stress, or a lack of consistent routines. Nevertheless, the overall results reveal a strong level of home-based involvement, with parents playing a supportive role that complements what their children are learning at school.

These findings are in line with what has been observed in the previous literature that has expressed the importance of home-based parental engagement in determining student outcomes. Fan and [17] discovered that having parents who support emotionally and have a well-organized home setting leads students to have better grades as well as good social lives. Moreover, research by Hill and Tyson [18] emphasizes that parental engagement at home, including ensuring routines, setting expectations, and showing interest in children's well-being, has a more substantial impact than some school-based forms of involvement. Similarly, Desforges and Abouchaar [19] note that parental support in basic daily routines, such as preparing children for school, is directly linked to improved learning attitudes and behavior.

The results highlight a strong level of home-based involvement among parents, particularly in providing for their children's daily needs. Many parents show dedication to ensuring their children arrive at school well-fed, neat, and ready to learn, clear indicators of care and commitment. However, while most parents are highly supportive, some appear to face challenges in consistently enforcing rules and routines at home. This could reflect the growing demands on parents' time, differences in parenting styles, or difficulties in managing children's behavior. Despite these challenges, the data overall points to a high degree of parental engagement at home, with parents playing an essential role in reinforcing students' readiness for school.

This aligns with the literature on the impact of parental support at home. According to Aman et al. [20], when parents are involved in their children's lives through routine care and guidance, it contributes significantly to children's emotional security and academic performance. Similarly, Wilder [21] notes that even simple, consistent home-based actions, such as preparing children for school, can have lasting positive effects on their motivation and school behavior.

Furthermore, Raftery et al. [22] highlighted that parental involvement at home strengthens students' sense of responsibility and supports better adjustment in school environments.

Table 2 Level of Parental Involvement in Elementary School

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Home-Based Involvement Activities	4.11	High
School-Based Involvement Activities	4.00	High
Overall	4.05	High

It can be seen from Table 3 that students' outcomes ranged from satisfactory to outstanding. Based on the results, Kindergarten garnered the highest grade of 90.97, which is classified as outstanding performance, followed by Grades 2, 3, 4, and 6, which had very satisfactory performance, while Grades 1 and 5 had satisfactory performance. In general, the students' outcomes had an average of 86.09, which had a descriptive equivalent of very satisfactory performance.

The results reflect a generally positive trend in student academic outcomes, with most grade levels performing at satisfactory to outstanding levels. The outstanding performance at the kindergarten level may suggest the strong foundational support provided early in a child's education, potentially linked to highly involved teaching strategies and parental engagement. The very satisfactory ratings in the middle grade levels highlight a continued pattern of achievement, though some variations exist, possibly influenced by factors such as changes in curriculum difficulty, student adjustment, or teaching methods. Notably, even the lowest performing groups maintained satisfactory ratings, which still indicate competence and an acceptable level of mastery.

These results are supported by educational research that emphasizes the impact of early interventions and continuous academic support on student performance. According to Pianta et al. [23], early childhood education programs are crucial in shaping long-term academic success, which may explain the high performance at the kindergarten level. Meanwhile, Allday and Pakurar [24] note that consistent instructional strategies, teacher motivation, and student engagement across grade levels are essential for maintaining high academic standards. Variations in performance among grade levels may also reflect developmental and contextual differences, as discussed by Carolan [25], who pointed out that transitions in learning demands and classroom expectations can influence student achievement.

Table 3 Students' Outcome

Grade Level	Grade	Descriptive Equivalent
Kindergarten	90.97	Outstanding
Grade 1	84.16	Satisfactory
Grade 2	86.27	Very Satisfactory
Grade 3	85.38	Very Satisfactory
Grade 4	87.16	Very Satisfactory
Grade 5	84.77	Satisfactory
Grade 6	85.78	Very Satisfactory
Average	86.09	Very Satisfactory

Shown in Table 4 are tests of significant difference between parental involvement and grade level. Based on the results, there was no significant difference between parental involvement and grade level provided with a p-value of 0.057 (F-value = 2.060), which was greater than at 0.05 level of significance, resulting in a failure to reject the null hypothesis.

The analysis reveals that there is no significant difference in the level of parental involvement across different grade levels. This suggests that parents tend to maintain a relatively consistent level of involvement in their children's education regardless of whether their child is in the early or later years of elementary schooling. While one might expect engagement to vary depending on age-related needs or academic demands, the findings imply that parents, on average, value their role in supporting learning across all grade levels.

These results align with studies suggesting that parental involvement can be relatively stable across a child's elementary years. According to Goodall and Ghent [26], many parents develop consistent patterns of engagement based on their beliefs about parenting, their perceived role in their child's education, and the school's expectations, rather than being driven solely by the child's age or grade level. Furthermore, Epstein [27] emphasized that schools with well-established family engagement policies often see sustained involvement across all grade levels. Although some research, such as that by Galindo and Sheldon [28], notes slight shifts in involvement as children grow older, these changes are not always statistically significant.

Table 4 Test of significant difference in parental involvement when grouped according to grade level

Variable	F-value	p-value	Remarks
Parental Involvement	2.060	0.057	Not Significant

Shown in Table 5 are tests of a significant relationship between parental involvement and student outcomes. Based on the results, there was a significant relationship between parental involvement and student outcomes provided with a p-value of 0.010, which was less than the 0.05 level of significance, resulting in a rejection of the null hypothesis. Moreover, there was a negligible positive correlation between parental involvement and student outcomes provided with a correlation coefficient of 0.132.

The results reveal a statistically significant relationship between parental involvement and student outcomes, suggesting that even modest levels of engagement from parents can positively influence how students perform academically. While the correlation is classified as negligible, it still highlights a meaningful connection, indicating that when parents are involved in their children's education, students are more likely to perform better. This could be due to a variety of subtle but impactful factors such as consistent encouragement, regular communication with teachers, or support with learning at home.

This result is consistent with existing literature emphasizing the value of parental engagement in improving student academic performance. Jaynes [29], through a meta-analysis, concluded that parental involvement, ranging from checking homework to discussing school activities, has a statistically significant positive effect on student achievement across grade levels. Similarly, Fan and Williams [30] found that emotional support from parents, such as expressing interest in a child's progress, can lead to improved academic motivation and outcomes. Although some studies, like those of Hill and Tyson [31], acknowledge that the strength of this relationship may vary depending on the type of involvement or the student's age, the consensus remains that family engagement plays an essential role in shaping student success.

Table 5 Test of the significant relationship between parental involvement and student outcomes

Variables	Correlation coefficient	p-value	Remarks
Parental Involvement	0.132	0.010	Significant
Student Outcome			

4. Conclusion

The overall results of the study revealed that teachers employ a high level of motivational strategies such as parenting, communication, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and community collaboration, which appear to support students' academic outcomes that range from satisfactory to outstanding. Likewise, parents demonstrate consistent involvement, particularly in home-based activities, which further contributes to a positive learning environment. The parents tend to maintain a relatively consistent level of involvement in their children's education, regardless of whether their child is in the early or later years of elementary schooling. A significant yet negligible positive relationship exists between parental involvement and student outcomes. This suggests that even small efforts from both teachers and parents collectively contribute to meaningful academic progress among students.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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